

G1/S phase progression is regulated by PLK1 degradation through the CDK1/ β TrCP axis

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SHORT TITLE: Role of PLK1 stability in the G1/S transition

ABBREVIATIONS: APH, aphidicolin; But, butyrate; CHX, cycloheximide; DO-wl, yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp and Leu; DO-wlh, yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp, Leu and His; DTB, double thymidine block; E1, ubiquitin activating enzyme; E2, ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme; GA, geldanamycin; IP, immunoprecipitation; NE, nuclear extract; NP40, Nonidet P-40; PI, normal serum; PMSF, phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride; S100, cytosolic extract; Ub, ubiquitin.

ABSTRACT

Polo-like kinase 1 (PLK1) is a serine/threonine kinase involved in several stages of the cell cycle, including the entry and exit from mitosis, and cytokinesis. Furthermore, it has an essential role in the regulation of DNA replication. Together with cyclin A, PLK1 also promotes CDH1 phosphorylation to trigger its ubiquitination and degradation, allowing cell cycle progression. The PLK1 levels in different type of tumors are very high compared to normal tissues, which is consistent with its role in promoting proliferation. Therefore, several PLK1 inhibitors have been developed and tested for the treatment of cancer. Here, we further analyzed PLK1 degradation and found that cytoplasmic PLK1 is ubiquitinated and subsequently degraded by the SCF^{βTrCP}/proteasome. This procedure is triggered when HSP90 is inhibited with geldanamycin, which results in misfolding of PLK1. We also identified CDK1 as the major kinase involved in this degradation. Our work shows for the first time that HSP90 inhibition arrests cell cycle progression at the G1/S transition. This novel mechanism inhibits CDH1 degradation through CDK1-dependent PLK1 destruction by the SCF^{βTrCP}/proteasome. In these conditions, CDH1 substrates do not accumulate and cell cycle arrests, providing a novel pathway for regulation of the cell cycle at the G1-to-S boundary.

KEY WORDS: Cell cycle/ HSP90/ protein degradation/ ubiquitin ligase

INTRODUCTION

Polo-like kinase 1 (PLK1) is a major cell cycle regulator involved in different processes, including mitotic entry, centrosome maturation, bipolar spindle formation, chromosome segregation, mitotic exit and cytokinesis (1). To carry out its functions, PLK1 phosphorylates an important number of proteins that can be recognized by the so-called PBDs (Polo Box Domains) (2). During G2 phase, PLK1 activation is mediated by phosphorylation on its T-loop by Aurora A. Bora, a cofactor of this kinase, is phosphorylated by CDK1, and then interacts with PLK1 and facilitates its phosphorylation by Aurora A (3, 4).

PLK1 also plays a critical role in regulating DNA replication. In fact, it has been shown to phosphorylate a series of targets that are involved in the formation of the pre-replicative complex and DNA replication, during the G1 and S phases, respectively (5). Furthermore, PLK1 together with cyclin A promote CDH1 phosphorylation to trigger its ubiquitination and subsequent degradation by the proteasome (6). CDH1 is one of the substrate adaptor proteins of the APC/C (anaphase promoting complex/cyclosome) ubiquitin ligase. During anaphase, dephosphorylation of CDH1 allows the formation of active APC/C^{CDH1} and the complex's activity persists until CDH1 is inactivated at the G1 to S transition through its phosphorylation and degradation (7).

PLK1 protein levels increase as cells progress from G1 to M phase (8) and are regulated by proteasome degradation. Both APC/C and SCF (SKP1/CUL1/F-box protein) ubiquitin ligases are involved in PLK1 ubiquitination and degradation. APC/C^{CDH1} controls PLK1 degradation from late anaphase, for the proper control of mitotic exit and cytokinesis, to the entry of cells into the G1 phase, and also after DNA-damage in G2 (9-11); whereas SCF^{FBXW7} controls nuclear PLK1 degradation in the G1 and S phases of an unperturbed cell cycle and in S phase following UV irradiation (12).

Most genetic alterations that promote tumorigenesis or increase the level of tumor cell proliferation involve dysregulation of the G0/G1 to S phase transition (13, 14): activating Ras mutations, inactivation of p53 or Rb, Myc overexpression or the loss of PTEN are just a few examples. PLK1 is overexpressed in a variety of human neoplastic tissues, including breast, ovarian, prostate, pancreatic, non-small-cell lung, head and neck, esophageal, gastric, endometrial, colorectal, bladder and thyroid cancer; melanomas; glioma; papillary carcinoma; hepatoma; leukemia and lymphoma (15). Therefore, PLK1 is proposed as a prognostic factor for human cancers (16).

Furthermore, as PLK1 expression in normal cells is very weak (17), it is used as a target

for the development of cancer-specific small molecule drugs. In fact, a number of PLK1 inhibitors have been discovered, some of which are being tested in clinical trials (18). In this report, we study the stability of PLK1 in relation to the G0/G1 to S phase transition. Starting with the analysis of the effect of geldanamycin (GA) on PLK1, we discovered the implication of a new ubiquitin ligase on PLK1 degradation. We found that SCF^{βTrCP} ubiquitinates cytoplasmic PLK1 for its degradation via the proteasome from G1- to S-phases of the cell cycle, and we determined the kinases that regulate this process. Finally, we examined the role of this degradation on cell cycle progression.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plasmids, cloning, point mutations and sequencing

pFlagCMV2-PLK1, pCMVHA-PLK1, pCMVHA-PLK1-T214G, pCS2HA-βTrCP, pCS2HA-βTrCPΔF, pGBT-Snf1, pGAD-Snf4 and empty vectors have been previously described (12, 19-21). pEGFP-N1 and pCW7 (pRG4Myc-Ub) were from BD Biosciences and ATCC, respectively. pCMVHA-CDK1, and the two-hybrid vectors pGBT10-βTrCP and pGAD-PLK1 were obtained by cloning the corresponding PCR fragments in pCMVHA, pGBT10, and pGADGH, respectively. Flag-PLK1-DB (R337A/L340A) and Flag-PLK1-S71A/D72G were constructed using the QuickChange II XL Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit from Stratagene. The sequences of constructs and point mutations were verified on both strands with an automatic sequencer.

Yeast two-hybrid methods

Saccharomyces cerevisiae strain Hf7c was cotransformed with the indicated plasmids by the lithium acetate method (21). Double transformants were plated on yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp and Leu (DO-wl). They were grown for 3 days at 30°C, and then colonies were patched on the same medium and replica-plated on yeast drop-out medium lacking Trp, Leu, and His (DO-wlh). Plasmids pGBT-Snf1 and pGAD-Snf4, carrying proteins that interact with each other, were used as controls (21).

Cell culture, cell synchronization, transient transfections and drugs

Routinely, HeLa, Cos-7, U2OS, MCF7, HEK293T, and A549 cells (from ATCC) were grown in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (BioWest) as described (22). Cells

enriched in the different phases of the cell cycle were also obtained as previously described (23), and confirmed by flow cytometry. DNA constructs were transiently transfected by electroporation and, 18h post-transfection, cells were harvested and lysed. Where appropriate, transfected cells were retransfected with other plasmids. In indicated experiments, cells were pretreated with the proteasome inhibitor MG132 (20 μ M, Sigma), cycloheximide (CHX 50 μ g/ml, Sigma), butyrate (6 mM, Sigma), aphidicolin (APH 1 μ M, Sigma), RO-3306 (9 μ M, Santa Cruz Biotechnology) or geldanamycin (GA 0.5-1.5 μ M, Santa Cruz Biotechnology), and harvested at various times.

Subcellular fractionation and lysis

Subcellular fractionation was carried out as described (21). Whole cell extracts were prepared at 4° C in 420 mM NaCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 1% Nonidet P-40 (NP40), 10% glycerol, 1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF), 1 μ g/ml aprotinin, 1 μ g/ml pepstatin, 1 μ g/ml leupeptin and 10 μ g/ml chymostatin for 20 min. Extracts were centrifuged at 20,000g for 20 min and supernatants frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80° C. Protein concentration was determined using the Bradford assay (Bio-Rad).

Knockdown experiments

Cells were interfered with β TrCP1/2-, FBXW7 α -, CDK1- or GSK3 β -siRNA (24-26) using the Oligofectamine method (Invitrogen) to suppress the expression of endogenous genes. EGFP-siRNA (24) was used as a non-specific control. Cells were harvested 48 h post-transfection and the reduction of protein levels confirmed by Western blotting.

Electrophoresis, Western blot analysis and antibodies

Proteins were separated by SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and gels were electroblotted onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed with the following antibodies: anti-HA-peroxidase monoclonal antibody (Roche); anti-hPTTG and anti-cyclin E monoclonal antibodies, and anti-WEE1 and anti-SKP2 polyclonal antibodies (Santa Cruz Biotechnology); anti- α -Tubulin and anti-Flag monoclonal antibodies (Sigma); anti-GFP polyclonal antibody (Immune Systems Ltd.); anti-CDK1 monoclonal and anti-MCM2 polyclonal antibodies (Cell Signaling); anti-PLK1 monoclonal antibody (Millipore); anti CDH1 monoclonal, and anti-NBS1 and anti-Aurora A

polyclonal antibodies (Novus); anti-Myc monoclonal antibody (Clontech); anti-cyclin A, anti-cyclin B, anti- β -catenin and anti-GSK3 β monoclonal antibodies (BD Biosciences); and anti-cyclin D1 polyclonal antibody (Abcam). Peroxidase-coupled donkey anti-rabbit IgG and sheep anti-mouse IgG were obtained from GE Healthcare. Immunoreactive bands were visualized using the Enhanced Chemiluminescence Western blotting system (ECL, GE Healthcare).

Flow cytometric analysis of cell cycle (FACS)

For cell cycle analysis, HeLa or A549 cells were collected after different treatments, washed with cold PBS twice, and fixed overnight in 70% cold ethanol at -20° C. Propidium iodide staining of nuclei was performed with a CycleTest Plus DNA reagent kit (BD Biosciences), and the DNA content was measured with a FACScan instrument (BD Biosciences). Data were acquired with CellQuest Pro software (BD Biosciences).

Co-immunoprecipitation experiments

Whole cell extracts diluted to 150 mM NaCl (1-2 mg) were incubated with normal mouse or rabbit sera (Santa Cruz Biotechnology) for 30 minutes and subsequently with protein G- or A-sepharose beads (GE Healthcare), respectively, for 1 hour at 4° C. After centrifugation, the beads were discarded and the supernatants incubated for 2 hours with anti-PLK1 (Millipore) or anti-HA (Covance) mouse monoclonal antibodies or anti- β TrCP rabbit monoclonal antibody (Cell Signaling) followed by protein G- or A-sepharose beads, respectively, for 1 hour. Alternatively, the supernatants were incubated with normal mouse or rabbit sera. Beads were washed and bound proteins were solubilized by the addition of SDS-sample buffer heated at 95° C for 5 minutes.

***In vitro* and *in vivo* ubiquitination assays**

The *in vitro* ubiquitination of wt or mutated PLK1 was performed in a volume of 10 μ l containing 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.6), 5 mM MgCl₂, 0.6 mM DTT, 2 mM ATP, 2 μ l *in vitro* transcribed/translated unlabeled F-box protein, 1.5 ng/ μ l E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme, Boston Biochem), 10 ng/ μ l His₆-UbcH3 (E2, Boston Biochem), 10 ng/ μ l UbcH5a (E2, Boston Biochem), 2.5 μ g/ μ l ubiquitin (Sigma), 1 μ M ubiquitin aldehyde (Boston Biochem), and 1 μ l ³⁵S-methionine-labelled *in vitro* transcribed/translated wt or mutated PLK1 as substrate. The reactions were incubated at

30° C for 1 hour and analyzed by SDS-PAGE and autoradiography. For some experiments the unlabeled F-box protein was substituted by a recombinant SCF^{βTrCP} complex expressed in Sf21 insect cells.

The *in vivo* ubiquitination experiments were performed in Cos-7 or HEK293T cells transfected and treated with MG132 4 hours before harvesting. Cells were washed in PBS, lysed at 95° C for 15 minutes in NP40 buffer supplemented with 5% SDS and 10 mM iodoacetamide, and diluted in NP40 buffer supplemented with 10 mM iodoacetamide. PLK1 was immunoprecipitated and proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE, electroblotted and probed with different antibodies.

RESULTS

Geldanamycin induces a transient degradation of PLK1 in HeLa cells

Geldanamycin (GA) is a benzoquinone ansamycin that specifically inhibits heat-shock protein 90 (HSP90) by competing with ATP for the ATP/ADP-binding pocket (27). Consequently, HSP90 becomes inactivated in its chaperone function that is required for client stabilization. Among these clients are PLK1 and CDK1, two cell cycle regulator kinases (28, 29). In mitosis GA-induced HSP90 inactivation leads to a PLK1-dependent cell cycle arrest preventing cell division (30). Treatment of HeLa cells with GA induced a transient reduction of PLK1 levels (Fig. 1A and Supplemental Fig. S1) that was reversed by proteasome inhibition (Fig. 1B). Interestingly, recovery of PLK1 levels also coincided with CDK1 degradation due to GA (Fig. 1A). To elucidate the ubiquitin ligase involved in the PLK1 degradation induced by GA, two specific PLK1 mutants were constructed and their behavior studied after GA treatment: PLK1-DB, which impedes its APC/C-dependent ubiquitination and degradation (10), and PLK1-T214G, which prevent SCF^{FBXW7}-dependent ubiquitination and degradation of the protein (12). APC/C and SCF^{FBXW7} are both members of the RING finger ubiquitin ligase family (31) involved in PLK1 degradation. Since GA also inhibits the ability of NF-κB to bind DNA thereby reducing the expression of genes (including those that are cloned into expression vectors) (32), we previously tested whether PLK1 transfected cells could be used to analyze GA induced degradation. GA treatment of HeLa cells transfected with pFlagCMV2-PLK1 (or pCMVHA-PLK1) induced the degradation of PLK1-tagged protein and this effect was avoided by blocking proteasome with MG132 (Fig. 1C). Therefore, these data indicate that GA did not alter the expression of promoters in our

conditions. Similar results were obtained when cells were pretreated with cycloheximide (CHX) to bypass the potential transcriptional effect of GA (Fig. 1D). Moreover, this last experiment also showed that HSP90 is effectively required for maintaining PLK1 stability, because its inhibition with GA increased the PLK1 degradation when translation was arrested with CHX (second vs. third lanes). However, both PLK1-DB and PLK1-T214G were degraded after GA treatment (Fig. 1E); therefore, neither APC/C nor SCF^{FBXW7} are implicated in PLK1 degradation after GA treatment.

β TrCP binds to PLK1 and promotes its ubiquitination both *in vitro* and *in vivo*

We previously observed that SCF ^{β TrCP} induced a slight ubiquitination of PLK1 *in vitro* (12). PLK1 possesses a potential non-canonical β TrCP-binding motif in the amino-terminal part of the protein. To further investigate whether SCF ^{β TrCP} is a new ubiquitin ligase for PLK1, co-immunoprecipitation experiments were performed to determine whether PLK1 interacts with β TrCP, the substrate recognition subunit of the SCF ^{β TrCP} ubiquitin ligase (33). Immunoprecipitation of both endogenous and transfected β TrCP was able to bring down endogenous PLK1 (Fig. 2A), and, reciprocally, PLK1 immunocomplexes co-precipitated HA- β TrCP (Fig. 2B). The yeast two-hybrid system, a binary method that can determine direct interactions between paired proteins (34), was used to analyze the β TrCP/PLK1 interaction and demonstrated that the proteins interact directly (Fig. 2C). Next, we analyzed the ability of SCF ^{β TrCP} to ubiquitinate PLK1 both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. We examined the *in vitro* ubiquitination of transcribed and translated ³⁵S-labeled PLK1 by SCF ^{β TrCP} from reticulocytes extracts (Fig. 2D) and from recombinant proteins produced in insect cells (Fig. 2E). In both cases, high molecular weight ubiquitinated forms of PLK1 were detected. To confirm that SCF ^{β TrCP} also promotes the PLK1 ubiquitination *in vivo*, Cos-7 cells were transfected and an increase of PLK1 poly-ubiquitination was avoided when cells were transfected with β TrCP Δ F (Fig. 2F), a dominant negative variant of β TrCP lacking the domain that couples the F-box protein to the SCF complex (20). Together, these results show that PLK1 is a new substrate of the SCF ^{β TrCP} E3 ubiquitin ligase.

SCF ^{β TrCP} induces proteasomal degradation of PLK1

Next, we investigated whether SCF^{βTrCP}-dependent PLK1 ubiquitination altered the stability of the protein. HeLa (or U2OS) cells were interfered with siRNA-βTrCP1/2 and an increase of PLK1 levels three times higher than that obtained for cells interfered with negative control siRNA-EGFP was observed (Fig. 3A and Supplemental Fig. S2). This increase was greater than that observed for WEE1, a known substrate of SCF^{βTrCP} (35). To discard a potential indirect effect of βTrCP depletion on PLK1 due to transcriptional activation of *PLK1* gene, we blocked translation with CHX and analyzed PLK1 levels from cells depleted of βTrCP. Figure 3B shows that PLK1 turnover was lower when cells were interfered with siRNA-βTrCP1/2 than when they were interfered with mock siRNA. Furthermore, βTrCP overexpression induced PLK1 degradation, which was largely avoided by inhibition of the proteasome (Fig. 3C). Lastly, to find out where and when SCF^{βTrCP} induced PLK1 ubiquitination and degradation, we performed two complementary experiments. HeLa cells were interfered with siRNA-βTrCP1/2 (or siRNA-EGFP) and cytosolic and nuclear fractions prepared. Figure 3D proves that, unlike SCF^{FBXW7} (12), SCF^{βTrCP} induced PLK1 degradation in the cellular cytosol. We also found that the amount of PLK1 augmented in the G1 and S phases of the cell cycle (butyrate- and aphidicolin-treated cells, respectively) of βTrCP-interfered cells, while, as an internal control, WEE1 increased in all phases of the cell cycle (Fig. 3E, F). We can conclude that SCF^{βTrCP} induces proteasomal degradation of PLK1 in the cytoplasm of cells from the G1- to S-phases of the cell cycle.

SCF^{βTrCP} negatively regulates PLK1 stability after geldanamycin treatment

With the aim of confirming whether SCF^{βTrCP} is the E3 ubiquitin ligase responsible for PLK1 degradation after treatment with GA, HeLa cells were interfered with siRNA-βTrCP1/2 (or with siRNA-FBXW7α as an internal control) and treated with GA for 4 hours. We found that depletion of βTrCP impeded the PLK1 degradation (Fig. 4A). Moreover, we discovered that *βTrCP* interference also prevented the GA-induced WEE1 degradation and, as expected, FBXW7α depletion increased the basal PLK1 levels but did not reverse the GA effect. GA-induced PLK1 degradation was also carried out in the cytoplasm (Fig. 4B) and from the G1- to S-phases (Fig. 4C), as induced by SCF^{βTrCP}. Confirming these results, a single putative βTrCP-recognition motif was found in the primary structure of PLK1 between residues 71 and 77 (Fig.

4D). To ascertain whether this site is the responsible for β TrCP-dependent degradation of PLK1, the potentially phosphorylated serine 71 was substituted with alanine and the aspartic acid 72 with glycine, generating the PLK1-S71A/D72G mutant. The PLK1-S71A/D72G mutant was significantly more stable in conditions of β TrCP overexpression than the wild type (wt) protein or other point mutants (Fig. 4E). Furthermore, *in vitro* ubiquitination assays showed that poly-ubiquitination of the mutant was considerably reduced compared with the wt (Fig. 4F and Supplemental Fig. S3). Finally, the effect of GA on PLK1-S71A/D72G stability was investigated and the mutant was found to be insensitive to degradation by GA (Fig. 4G). Together, these results demonstrate that SCF ^{β TrCP} negatively regulates PLK1 stability after GA treatment.

The degradation of PLK1 is dependent on CDK1 and GSK3 β

A number of studies have demonstrated that GSK3 β phosphorylates a cluster of Ser/Thr residues in target proteins, which are then recognized by SCF ^{β TrCP} (36-39). The β TrCP motif of PLK1 includes the consensus S/T-X-X-X-S/T phosphoacceptor sequence for GSK3 β (40). Consequently, we decided to analyze the involvement of this kinase in PLK1 degradation. We depleted GSK3 β in HeLa and A549 cells using siRNA and found an increase of PLK1 levels similar to that obtained with siRNA- β TrCP (Fig. 5A). As a control we analyzed the levels of WEE1, which only augmented with β TrCP depletion. However, when we explored whether depletion of GSK3 β could prevent the PLK1 degradation induced by GA treatment, we observed that although PLK1 levels were increased, this did not impede the GA induced PLK1 degradation (Fig. 5B). Since in Figure 1A we noticed an inverse correlation between the amount of PLK1 and CDK1 after GA treatment, we studied the potential role of this kinase in PLK1 degradation. We overexpressed CDK1 in HeLa cells and analyzed its effect on PLK1 levels after GA treatment. Figure 5C shows that *CDK1* transfection not only enhanced PLK1 degradation, but also clearly delayed the PLK1 recovery observed when cells transfected with empty vector were treated with GA. This effect was reflected in the cell cycle, delaying the recovery of the cycle progression after treatment with GA (Fig. 5D). This indicates that before CDK1 stability is affected by GA, this kinase regulates PLK1 degradation. To verify this result, we examined the influence of GA treatment in A549 cells. These cells express low levels of a functional mutant form of PLK1 that does not

interact with HSP90 and, therefore, is not affected by GA (41). Any changes in PLK1 stability in these cells cannot be caused directly by GA, but would rather correlate with the CDK1 diminution caused by GA. Figure 5E shows that reduction of CDK1 induced an increase of PLK1 (third and fourth lanes) and the increase of CDK1 correlated with a decrease of PLK1 (fifth lane). This implies that GA provokes a CDK1-dependent PLK1 degradation, whose destruction finishes when CDK1 is itself degraded. Similar results were obtained when CDK1 was inhibited with RO-3306, a selective CDK1 inhibitor (Supplemental Fig. S4).

Finally, to confirm that β TrCP is implicated in this degradation, A549 cells were transfected with β TrCP Δ F with or without RO-3306 treatment during 4 hours. The increase of PLK1 induced by CDK1 inhibition was avoided by the presence of the negative dominant β TrCP (Fig. 5F). To rule out the limited effect of CDK1 inhibition on cell cycle distribution, we studied WEE1 levels. Similar to PLK1, WEE1 levels rise between the G1 and G2 phase of the cell cycle and then fall during M phase due to decreased synthesis and proteolytic degradation (42, 43). We found that RO-3303 treatment for 4 hours did not significantly alter cell cycle distribution (compare first and second or third and fourth lanes). Moreover, CDK1 expression increased PLK1 ubiquitination by SCF ^{β TrCP} both *in vivo* and *in vitro* (Fig. 5G, H). Taken together, our results demonstrated that i) the degradation of PLK1 is dependent on CDK1 and GSK3 β under normal growing conditions, and ii) CDK1 is a major kinase involved in PLK1 degradation by SCF ^{β TrCP}/proteasome when the protein is not properly folded.

HSP90 regulates the G1/S transition and cell cycle progression in a PLK1-dependent manner

Taking into account all our observations, we decided to analyze the cell cycle effect of the PLK1 degradation induced by GA in the G1 and S phases.

We synchronized HeLa and A549 cells at late G1 by double thymidine block and incubated for 4 hours with or without GA before releasing into thymidine-free media. In HeLa cells (Fig. 6A and Supplemental Fig. 5A), PLK1 degradation by GA induced a transient delay of approximately 4 hours in cell cycle progress (compare the *4h after thymidine release* and *10h after thymidine release + GA* bars in Fig. 6A). However, in A549 cells, no significant delay was evident between GA treated and control cells (Fig. 6B and Supplemental Fig. 5B). These results were confirmed by Western blots

analyzing proteins that are involved in the regulation of the cell cycle (Fig. 6C, D). Interestingly, this delay matches the time period during which GA induced the degradation of PLK1 (Fig. 1A), suggesting a control of cell cycle progression through PLK1 stability.

As we have previously indicated, PLK1 (in addition to cyclin A) is an upstream modifying enzyme that promotes CDH1 phosphorylation to trigger its ubiquitination and degradation (6). The consequence of this pathway is the accumulation of CDH1 substrates allowing cell cycle progression from G1-to-S phase. To elucidate the effect of PLK1 degradation on the G1/S transition, we arrested HeLa cells in early G1 phase with butyrate (44), and 4 hours before releasing from the block, cells were treated or not with GA. We found that HeLa cells began to progress towards S/G2 8 hours after butyrate release, whereas cells released from butyrate but treated with GA remained arrested in the G1 phase (Fig. 6E). This result indicates that PLK1 is required for G1-to-S phase progression. To confirm this hypothesis, we studied CDH1 levels and some CDH1 substrates after GA treatment in cells expressing the non-degradable by SCF^{βTrCP} PLK1 mutant. We transfected HeLa cells with PLK1 (as a control) or PLK1-S71A/D72G, and arrested cells with butyrate for 18 hours, released from the block for 4 hours and treated or not with GA for 4 more hours. We found that PLK1 degradation induced by GA provoked an increase of CDH1 and a corresponding decrease of APC/C^{CDH1} substrates. However, overexpression of PLK1-S71A/D72G inhibited this effect (Fig. 6F). These results are consistent with those observed by flow cytometry, since APC/C^{CDH1} substrates must accumulate to promote cell cycle progression from G1 to S phase. In this way, transient transfection of the PLK1 mutant abrogated, at least partially, the G1/S phase transition defects caused by GA (Fig. 6G). Therefore, our results strongly support the notion that cells delay cell cycle progression when PLK1 is not properly folded, destroying it via the βTrCP/proteasome, which, in turn, prevents CDH1 degradation.

DISCUSSION

Most of the studies on PLK1 have focused on different aspects of late G2 and mitosis (45). However, increasing numbers of publications are appearing on the role of PLK1 in DNA replication. These reports claim an essential role of PLK1 during G1 and S phases (5). In a similar vein, Wei and coworkers emphasize the role of PLK1 in CDH1 degradation for cell cycle progression from G1 to S phases (6). Considering the effects

of PLK1 overexpression (or accumulation of the protein) in tumors (15), we dedicated our study to analyze PLK1 stability outside of G2/M. We found that when PLK1 does not have the proper conformation, it is degraded by the proteasome through the CDK1/ β TrCP axis. This allows a precise control of CDH1, which, in turn, regulates the stability of proteins involved in G1 to S phase progression (Fig. 7). Importantly, APC/C deregulation may lead to genomic instability and cancer.

APC/C^{CDH1} remains active from anaphase to G1/S transition, and targets cyclins and other cell cycle regulatory proteins for proteasomal degradation (46). In S phase, APC/C is inactivated, allowing accumulation of the cyclins and the cell cycle to progress (6, 47). In fact, premature activation of APC/C results in destabilization of geminin and cyclin A, two proteins that prevent re-replication in mammalian cells, and activates the DNA damage checkpoint pathways (48). Conversely, stable suppression of CDH1 causes the aberrant accumulation of most CDH1 target proteins, which control accurate and equal distribution of the genetic information to daughter cells (49). Our results corroborate these observations showing that overexpression of a GA non-degradable PLK1 mutant avoided CDH1 accumulation in these conditions, and consequently, degradation of its substrates, SKP2 and Aurora A, between others, promoting the cell cycle progression.

HSP90 is a molecular chaperone responsible for the stability and function of a wide variety of client proteins that are critical for cell growth and survival. Among these clients are a number of oncoproteins, attaching a great importance to its role.

We found in HeLa cells, and others groups found in CHL-1, EBC-1 and A375 cells (50), a clear reduction in PLK1 levels at early time points after HSP90 inhibition. However, after a prolonged GA (or XL888) treatment, PLK1 levels increased and even surpassed the basal level, coinciding with a cell cycle arrest in G2/M. We now know that this increase is not due to a desensitization of PLK1 to HSP90, as was previously suggested (50), but rather due to CDK1 degradation, whose phosphorylation directly or indirectly is required for PLK1 ubiquitination and degradation. Other cell lines, such as Colo205 or MCF7, treated with herbimycin A, an ansamycin antibiotic similar to GA, arrested in G1 phase (51), but these cells probably possess a potent G1/S checkpoint, that is absent in HeLa cells. In fact, the normal function of the p53- and retinoblastoma-mediated G1/S checkpoint is inactivated in HeLa cells due to expression of HPV-encoded E6 and E7 oncoproteins (52). Therefore, in these cells, arrest in G1/S results in

a delay in cell cycle progression causing arrest at the next checkpoint, G2/M (Supplemental Fig. 6).

Taking our results and those reported by other groups, we can conclude that GA arrests cell cycle progression at least at three levels: i) GA produces CDK1-dependent PLK1 degradation by SCF^{βTrCP}/proteasome triggering a cell cycle arrest in G1/S. ii) GA also induces a G2/M arrest due to CDK1 degradation (Fig. 1A, Fig. 6B, and (29)), and a compromised activity of PLK1. Indeed, when exponential-growing cells were treated with GA, PLK1 stability and/or activity, probably depending on the cell line, was affected (28). The direct consequence of this arrest is the reduction or absence of the microtubule nucleating activity. iii) After metaphase-to-anaphase transition, HSP90 inhibition leads to a PLK1-dependent APC/C inactivation by both dephosphorylation and activation of spindle assembly checkpoint (30) arresting cell cycle. As a result, cells show severe mitotic aberrations. Furthermore, there could still be a fourth level of regulation that has not yet been explored in depth. When we compared the cell cycle progression of HeLa and A549 cells after thymidine release and GA treatment (Fig. 6), we observed that cell progression of the S phase in HeLa cells was slowed, whereas no significant delay was evident in A549 cells. This suggests that PLK1 degradation is also involved in S phase progression. This delay could be a consequence of PLK1's own role in replication or due to its effects on protein degradation involved in cell cycle progression in S phase. The precise molecular mechanism governing this effect remains to be explored.

In the present study, the importance of βTrCP on PLK1 stability was studied when HSP90 was inhibited by GA. But these results could probably be extended to other conditions where the function of HSP90 is compromised. HSP90 launches a rapid response to environmental insults such as heat, hypoxia, UV and gamma-radiation, reactive oxygen intermediates, and injury-induced growth factors to maintain protein homeostasis and viability (53). Nevertheless, when stress conditions exceed the capacity of chaperone proteins, cells should have mechanisms to prevent cell progression. It is probably in this context where SCF^{βTrCP} fulfills its normal physiological role, ubiquitinating and degrading PLK1, perhaps among others. Thus, the aggregation of misfolded or unfolded proteins is prevented and the cell cycle is arrested. Otherwise, protein accumulation would result in proteotoxic stress (54).

The fine control exercised by HSP90 on cell cycle regulation leads us to confirm that inhibition of PLK1 function, in particular, or of HSP90, in general, will become an

essential tool for cancer therapy. Not surprisingly, HSP90 has recently been identified as an interesting target for anticancer drugs and several PLK1 and HSP90 inhibitors are in different phases of clinical trials and show promising therapeutic value (55, 56).

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

SG and MG-M performed the main experiments and analyzed data. CL-M and ACR prepared subcellular fractions and synchronized cell cultures. JH-R and MM-S carried out co-immunoprecipitation experiments. CS and MAJ performed FACS analysis and contributed to the discussion of the results. MT and FR designed the research and wrote the manuscript with input from all other authors.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Geldanamycin (GA) induces a transient PLK1 degradation by the proteasome. (A) HeLa cells were incubated with GA (1 μ M) for the indicated times, and whole extracts analyzed by Western blotting. C: whole cell extract from non-treated HeLa cells. The bottom panel shows quantification of PLK1 and CDK1 protein levels presented in (A) using the ImageJ software. Error bars represent the SD (n=3). (B) HeLa cells were treated with GA (1 μ M) and/or MG132 for 4 h before harvesting. Lysates were analyzed by immunoblotting. (C) HeLa cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and distributed in four plates. After 18 h, cells were treated with GA (1 μ M) and/or MG132 for 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were analyzed by Western blotting. (D) HeLa cells were transfected with pCMVHA-PLK1 and distributed in plates. After 18 h, CHX was added to the medium, and then MG132 and GA. Cells were collected 4 h later and whole cell extracts analyzed by Western blot. (E) PLK1 mutants were generated by point mutagenesis; plasmids were transfected in HeLa cells, and cells were treated and analyzed as in (C).

Figure 2. β TrCP interacts directly with PLK1 *in vivo* and promotes its poly-ubiquitination. (A) Whole cell extracts from HeLa or Cos-7 transfected cells were used to immunoprecipitate β TrCP (right panels) or HA β TrCP (left panels), respectively, and complexes were analyzed by immunoblotting. IP-PI: immunoprecipitation with normal rabbit (right panels) or mouse (left panels) sera. (B) Similarly, Cos-7 transfected cells were used to immunoprecipitate PLK1, and complexes were analyzed by Western blotting. IP-PI: immunoprecipitation with normal mouse serum. (C) β TrCP interacts with PLK1 in a yeast two-hybrid assay. Hf7c reporter strain was cotransformed with the indicated constructs. The interaction between the two-hybrid proteins is indicated by growth in the absence of histidine, DO-wlh (dark red patch). Snf1/Snf4 interaction was used as a positive control. (D) *In vitro* ubiquitin ligation assay of 35 S-labeled *in vitro*-transcribed/translated PLK1 was conducted in the presence or absence of cold *in vitro*-transcribed/translated β TrCP, E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme), E2 (His₆-UbcH3 and UbcH5a), and Ub (ubiquitin). Samples were incubated at 30° C for 1 h. The bracket on the right marks a ladder of bands corresponding to poly-ubiquitinated PLK1. (E) Experiment performed as in (D), except the unlabeled F-box protein was substituted by

a recombinant SCF^{βTrCP} complex expressed in Sf21 insect cells. (F) Cos-7 cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and treated with MG132 for 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were prepared and poly-ubiquitinated PLK1 visualized after Western blot of the PLK1 immunoprecipitations.

Figure 3. βTrCP induces proteasomal degradation of cytoplasmic PLK1 from G1-to-S phases of the cell cycle. (A) HeLa cells were interfered with the indicated siRNAs and extracts were blotted with the indicated antibodies. (B) Cells were interfered with EGFP- or βTrCP-siRNA. After 48 h, CHX was added to the medium and cells were collected 10 h later. Extracts were analyzed by Western blot. (C) Whole cell extracts from HeLa cells transfected with the indicated plasmids and treated or not with MG132 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were migrated, electroblotted, and probed with the indicated antibodies. (D) HeLa cells interfered with siRNA-βTrCP or siRNA-EGFP were used to prepare cytosolic (S100) and nuclear extracts (NE). The fractions were analyzed for the presence of different proteins, as indicated. (E) HeLa cells were interfered with siRNA-βTrCP or siRNA-EGFP, and synchronized in the different phases of the cell cycle. Extracts were analyzed by Western blot. (F) Quantification of PLK1 and WEE1 protein levels presented in (E) using the ImageJ software. Error bars represent the SD (n=3). The quantitative fold change in PLK1 was determined relative to the loading control.

Figure 4. GA induces βTrCP-dependent PLK1 degradation. (A) HeLa cells were interfered with the indicated siRNAs and treated or not with GA 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were analyzed by Western blot. (B) HeLa cells, treated or not with GA for 4 h, were used to prepare cytosolic (S100) and nuclear extracts (NE), and fractions were analyzed for the presence of different proteins. (C) Cells were synchronized in the different phases of the cell cycle and treated or not with GA for 4 h. Extracts were blotted with the indicated antibodies. LE: Low exposition. HE: High exposition. The graph shows the quantification of PLK1 protein levels using the ImageJ software. Error bars represent the SD (n=3). (D) Alignment of βTrCP consensus sequences from different βTrCP substrates and localization of a putative βTrCP motif in PLK1 (residues 71 to 77). Arrows indicate the amino acid changes performed to obtain the mutation of PLK1 in this motif (PLK1-S71A/D72G). In the βTrCP consensus sequence, X refers to

any amino acid. (E) Cos-7 cells were transfected with plasmids encoding wild type (wt) PLK1 or point mutants, and 18 h later re-transfected with the indicated plasmids. Extracts were blotted with different antibodies. The quantitative fold change in PLK1 was determined relative to level of EGFP. (F) *In vitro* ubiquitin ligation assay of ³⁵S-labeled *in vitro*-transcribed/translated PLK1 or PLK1-S71A/D72G was conducted in the presence or absence of cold *in vitro*-transcribed/translated βTrCP, E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme), E2 (His₆-UbcH3 and UbcH5a), and Ub (ubiquitin). Samples were incubated at 30° C for 1 h. The bracket on the right marks a ladder of bands corresponding to poly-ubiquitinated PLK1 (wt or mutant). (G) HeLa transfected cells were treated or not with GA 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were analyzed by immunoblot.

Figure 5. CDK1 mediates PLK1 degradation induced by GA. (A) HeLa and A549 cells were interfered with the indicated siRNAs and either untreated (A) or treated with GA 4 h before harvesting (B). Protein levels were studied by Western blot. The quantitative fold change in PLK1 was determined relative to the loading control. (C) HeLa cells were transfected with pCMVHA or pCMVHA-CDK1 and, 18 h later, incubated with GA for the indicated times. Extracts were prepared and analyzed by immunoblot. The graph shows the quantification of PLK1 protein levels using the ImageJ software. Error bars represent the SD (n=3). (D) HeLa cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and arrested in early G1 phase with butyrate (But). After 18 h, cells were treated with GA for 4 h and released from But block. Cells were collected at the indicated times and the cell cycle analyzed by FACS. The percentages of cells in G0/G1 or S/G2 are shown. (E) A549 cells were incubated with GA for the indicated times and whole extracts analyzed by Western blotting. C: whole cell extract from non-treated A549 cells. (F) A549 cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and treated or not with RO-3306 for 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were analyzed by immunoblot. (G) HEK293T cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids and treated with MG132 for 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were prepared and poly-ubiquitinated PLK1 visualized after Western blot of the PLK1 immunoprecipitations. (H) *In vitro* ubiquitin ligation assay of ³⁵S-labeled *in vitro*-transcribed/translated PLK1 was conducted in the presence or absence of cold *in vitro*-transcribed/translated βTrCP and CDK1, E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme), E2 (His₆-UbcH3 and UbcH5a), and Ub (ubiquitin).

Samples were incubated at 30° C for 1 h. The bracket on the right marks a ladder of bands corresponding to poly-ubiquitinated PLK1.

Figure 6. PLK1 stability regulates cell cycle progression through the G1/S phase. (A) HeLa and (B) A549 cells were synchronized in late G1 by double thymidine block (DTB). Four hours before release from the second thymidine block, cells were treated or not with GA. Cells were collected at the indicated times and the cell cycle analyzed by flow cytometry. The percentages of cells in each cell cycle phase are shown. (C) A portion of the harvested HeLa or (D) A549 cells (from (A) and (B), respectively) were analyzed by Western blot. (E) Similarly to (A), HeLa cells were arrested in early G1 phase with butyrate (But). After 18 h, cells were treated or not with GA for 4 h and released from But block. Cells were collected at the indicated times and the cell cycle analyzed by FACS. The percentages of cells in G0/G1 or S/G2 are shown. (F) HeLa cells were transfected with the indicated plasmids, and 18 h later arrested in G1 with butyrate. After 18 h, cells were released from arrest, and 4 h later, treated or not with GA for 4 h before harvesting. Extracts were studied by immunoblot. (G) Experiment performed as for (E) except the HeLa cells were previously transiently transfected as indicated.

Figure 7. A model of the regulation of G1/S cell cycle progression mediated by PLK1 stability. To enter in S phase, CDH1 must be phosphorylated by cyclin A/CDK2 and PLK1, ubiquitinated by SCF^{βTrCP} and degraded by the proteasome, allowing APC/C^{CDH1} substrates to accumulate. When PLK1 is unfolded, it is directly or indirectly phosphorylated by CDK1 and degraded by the SCF^{βTrCP}/proteasome. This inhibits CDH1 degradation and arrests cell cycle progression.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

G1/S phase progression is regulated by PLK1 degradation through the CDK1/ β TrCP axis by Servando Giráldez *et al.*

Supplemental Figure S1. Effect of different concentrations of geldanamycin (GA) on PLK1 levels in HeLa cells. HeLa cells were incubated with 0.5 μ M (A) or 1.5 μ M GA (B) for the indicated times and whole extracts analyzed by Western blot. C: whole cell extract from non-treated HeLa cells.

Supplemental Figure S2. Effect of β TrCP or FBXW7 α depletion on PLK1 protein levels. U2OS cells were interfered with the indicated siRNAs and extracts were blotted with antibodies against PLK1 and α -Tubulin.

Supplemental Figure S3. PLK1 S71A/D72G is not poly-ubiquitinated by SCF β TrCP. *In vitro* ubiquitin ligation assay of 35 S-labeled *in vitro*-transcribed/translated PLK1 S71A/D72G was conducted in the presence or absence of recombinant SCF β TrCP complex expressed in Sf21 insect cells, E1 (His₆-ubiquitin activating enzyme), E2 (His₆-UbcH3 and UbcH5a), and Ub (ubiquitin). Samples were incubated at 30° C for 1 h. The bracket on the right marks a ladder of bands corresponding to poly-ubiquitinated PLK1.

Supplemental Figure S4. Effect of CDK1 inhibition on PLK1 levels. A549 cells were treated with RO-3306 for 4 h, and extracts were analyzed by immunoblot.

Supplemental Figure S5. Effect of GA treatment on cell cycle of HeLa and A549 cells synchronized in late G1. (A) HeLa and (B) A549 cells were synchronized in late G1 by double thymidine block (DTB). Four hours before release from the second thymidine block, cells were treated or not with GA. Cells were collected at the indicated times and the cell cycle analyzed by flow cytometry.

Supplemental Figure S6. Effect of GA treatment on cell cycle of asynchronous HeLa and MCF7 cells. Asynchronous HeLa and MCF7 cells were treated with GA for the indicated times, collected and the cell cycle analyzed by flow cytometry.